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Nanotechnology in dentistry

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Introduction: Nanotechnology is an emerging interdisciplinary field that is undergoing rapid development and has brought about enormous changes in medicine and dentistry. The 3 major fields of applications are particularly targeted are diagnosis, drug administration and regenerative medicine. In the field of dentistry, nanotechnology is used for enamel remineralization, dental hypersensitivity, and development of dental restorative materials with enhanced properties. The studies on tooth structure provide a basis for nanotechnology-based dental treatments known as ‘nanodentistry’. The main idea of this paradigm shift is to provide good oral health by introducing new nanomaterials. As patients' treatment requirements continue to increase in aesthetics and functionality, a demanding challenge has been established in the field of engineered nanomaterials.

Literature review: The aim of nanodentistry is to mimic the natural tissue architecture (both soft and hard) in the place of lost tissue area due to disease using newly developed biomaterials. Nanomaterials are used in dental implants, in dental fillings, anti-sensitivity agent, teeth whitening, prevention of dental caries prophylactically and for polishing of enamel surfaces. Some particles which are commonly used in the dental field are Carbon nanotubes, Graphene, Hydroxyapatite, Iron Oxide, Zirconia, Silica, Titania, silver etc. All these nanomaterials are used in dental application as therapeutic means, for antimicrobial activity and for reinforcing or enhancing the present materials for better usage.

Conclusions: In conclusion nanotechnology in the future will become an essential part of the clinical dental practice. Nanomaterials used for better oral healthcare services will become less stressful for the dental surgeons. Nanomaterials attract patients towards dentistry, since it will be cost effective, time-saving and prevent the patient from mental trauma. Development of modified nanomaterials is surely going to help to solve the many dental problems.

Keywords: *Nanomaterials, Nanotechnology, Nanodentistry, Dental materials*

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